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TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS CASE STUDY ON THE PERINTIS KEMERDEKAAN STREETS OF MAKASSAR

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ABSTRACT: Makassar City is one of the major Cities in Indonesia with high of vehicle ownership rate. It provides one of the effects that traffic congestion, especially on Perintis Kemerdekaan Street, the which is an arterial road is the main route linking the economy of the Makassar city with several districts located in the north of Makassar. Therefore, this study is to assess the characteristics of the causes of traffic accidents on the Perintis Kemerdekaan Street in the period 2011 - 2015. In that time brackets have occurred 3,603 cases of traffic accidents in the resulting casualties as many as 4.654 people with material losses Reached IDR 9.4 billion. onr the Perintis Kemerdekaan Street, the type of vehicle that have high perenatg of accidents are motorcycle Reached 837 vehicles were dominated by a collision between a motorcycle as much as 195 events. Of the total accidents on this street during this period has been the victim has reached 959 people and the most dominant time events occurred on the morning that the hours 06:00 to 10:00.

Keywords: traffic accidents, vehicles, collision

INTRODUCTION

One of phenomenon that most often reported in the print media and on television is the case of traffic accidents. Currently, traffic accidents (traffic accident) are becoming a separate trend for urban living activities. As is known, the city synonymous with chaos, the abundance of motor vehicles and roads are inadequate for the large volume of vehicles. Although it did not also be denied, accidents in rural areas often also occur, but mostly not due to environmental factors such as the presence in the city.

Traffic accidents in Indonesia have become the third biggest killer. The number of deaths due to accidents is under coronary heart disease and tuberculosis, or TB. Based on data from the National Police, as many as 25 157 people died in 2013. Going down compared to 2012, 27,000 people died. While in 2011 the number of victims reached 32 657 inhabitants. This data shows the number of casualties caused by the accident is still very high. Based on these figures, the average victim died as a result of the accident about 80 people per day, or about four people per hour. World Health Organization (WHO) or the World Health Organization noted that every year the incidence of traffic accidents has resulted in an average of 1.24 million people died and some 50 million people suffered injuries and permanent disabilities. World Health Organization (WHO) or the World Health Organization noted that every year the incidence of traffic accidents has resulted in an average of 1.24 million people died and some 50 million people suffered injuries and permanent disabilities. (Prihiawito & Budiawati, 2014).

Makassar City as one of the biggest cities in Indonesia certainly has a lot of areas dense with a variety of activities such as industrial zones, commercial district, and educational areas and office. Based on the growth rate of the rate of accidents also increased significantly. Data from the city of Makassar Polrestabes noted that in 2015 recorded 810 events with a total of 1,223 people achieve the victim. From these data, it is known that the number of deaths resulting from traffic accidents 117 people, as many as 56 people were seriously injured, slightly injured 913 people and only suffered material losses as many as 133 people. And that is quite a concern is the whole incident was caused due to human factors. (Traffic Accident Unit, 2016).

One of the roads that have a fairly high level of congestion is a segment Perintis Kemerdekaan Road. This road is a connecting road between activity centers and is the main route connecting between Maros and Makassar. Perintis Kemerdekaan Road is also a primary arterial road so the possibility of traffic accidents is quite high, especially at rush hour (peak hour).

From the statistical data Polrestabes Makassar, for 2015 show that the incidence of traffic accidents on roads Perintis Kemerdekaan there were 127 cases with a fatality rate of 167 souls, including death, injury fallow and minor injuries. Material losses estimated at USD 314.9 million.

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This study aims to determine the characteristics and causes of traffic accidents on roads Perintis Kemerdekaan Makassar. Benefits to be gained from this study is to provide information on the cause of traffic accidents and an overview of the countermeasures, especially on roads Perintis Kemerdekaan in Makassar.

Definition of Accident

Many studies and the variety of definitions describes traffic accidents. In Indonesia, the definition of a traffic accident stipulated in Government Regulation No. 43 of 1993 and in Law No. 22 of 2009. The regulation explains that a traffic accident is an event in the way that unexpected and unintentional involving a moving vehicle with or without other road users, resulting in human casualties and property loss.

Adisasmita, (2010) suggested that the impact of traffic accidents can be classified by the accident victim into four levels, namely; a) Fatal Accident, was the victim of an accident which certainly died as a result of traffic accidents within a maximum period of 30 days after the accident; b) Serious Accidents are victims of accidents due to his injuries suffered permanent disability or hospitalization at the hospital in a period of more than 30 days since the accident occurred. An event is classed as permanent disability if something limbs missing or cannot be used at all and can not be cured or recovered forever; c) Light Accident is accident victims who suffered injuries that do not require hospitalization or to be admitted to hospital than 30 days; d) Material Losses, which only leads to accidents causing material losses.

Characteristics of Accident

According to Warpani (2002), the causes of traffic accidents can be grouped into four elements, namely: human, vehicle, road and environment. The percentage of each of these factors cause of traffic accidents in Indonesia, namely the human factor of 93.52%, a factor of vehicles by 2.76%, 3.23% roads factors, and environmental factors of 0.49%.

In the General Plan Land Transport Safety (2006) also describe the main cause of a traffic accident is influenced by the human factor, vehicle and road environment, as well as the interaction and combination of two or more factors mentioned above. It can be seen from Fig.1.

Fig. 1 The cause of the accident and their interactions

Next, we will discuss the factors that cause road traffic accidents, motorcycle riders include the human factor, vehicle, and physical environment.

Human factors

The human factor as the road, users can be divided into two groups, namely as a driver (driver) and as a pedestrian (pedestrian). Man is the most important factor and the greatest cause of traffic accidents. Driving is a complex task, which requires specific knowledge and abilities because at the same time the driver has to deal with the equipment and receive stimuli from the influence of his surroundings (Hobbs, 1995). It is also revealed by Murat Karacasu and Arzu Er (2011) in his study explains that the human factor is a major factor in traffic accidents range from 97-98%. This factor caused by human error or others, such as education level, age, gender and psychology.

Pedestrians are all road users without vehicles on the road. Frequent traffic accidents actually occur on the pedestrians either by mistake or pedestrians itself as an unlucky fall victim to someone else's fault.

Error pedestrians generally due to lax, non-compliance with the legislation and ignore the traffic manners. For example, not to cross the zebra crossing, walking paths using traffic (due to forgetfulness or forced) or other errors that cause accidents. Pedestrians often use the vehicle lane because sidewalks are pedestrian facilities be used by street vendors.

Characteristics of Vehicle

Factors vehicle is also one cause of traffic accidents. Factors that lead to frequent vehicle accidents can be caused by components of the vehicle are not working properly and a variety of other causes. Cause among others, can be caused by; a) brake; b) wheel; c) skid d) vehicle light

Characteristics of Roads and the Environment

The road condition can be one of the causes of traffic accidents. Although experts, design the road system and road design in such a way, but everything is back to man as the road itself. Driver behavior is a very decisive factor in traffic safety.

Factors road includes the condition of damaged roads, potholes, slippery, dark, with no markings/signs, and bend/incline/derivatives sharp, other than that the location of the road as in the city or outside the city (rural) and traffic volumes also affect the incidence traffic accident. While environmental factors derived from weather conditions (foggy, cloudy, and rainy). The interaction between the factors and environmental factors is what ultimately creates physical environmental factors that became one cause of traffic accidents.

Traffic Accident Prevention Methods

Given the complexity of the traffic system, it is necessary mitigation efforts traffic accident in a comprehensive manner so as to anticipate the factors contributing to the problem of traffic accidents. Methods of overcoming the problems of road safety can be carried out using 5 E covers the fields of engineering infrastructure and means of traffic (engineering), coaching (education), law enforcement (law enforcement), guidance / encouragement to behave safely (Encouragement), the handling of the accident victim right/emergency response (Tahir, 2006).

METHODOLOGY

Location of Study

The location study is taken from the Primary Arterial Road, which stretches from south to north. The road is an Perintis Kemerdekaan Street has a length of $\pm$ 15 km. The street conditions as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 The map of studies location

Data Sources

The data in this study consisted of primary and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained by direct observation in the study site, among others; a) observing the movement of vehicles passing through these roads; b) Observing location and the points that are considered prone to accidents such as locations that are around the public service facilities such as offices, education and housing, which indirectly contributes directly accidents because they are on the sides of the road. While secondary data is data obtained from departments or agencies, in this case the Traffic Accident Unit Polrestabes Makassar. Data were analyzed using statistical methods

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Overview of Makassar City Traffic Accidents

In Table 1, shows that the number of cases of traffic accidents in the city of Makassar in the period of last five years, reaching 4,806 cases with the highest number of cases reached 1,203 cases in 2011 and the lowest was 781 cases in 2014. The losses of material annually on average reached IDR 1,882,592,000 million and the number of victims as many as 1,261 people.

Table 1. Number of traffic accidents in the city of Makassar Year 2011-2015

No	Year	No. of cases	the number of traffic casualties			total (ppl)	material losses (IDR)	percentage
			Fatal	Serious	Slight			
1	2011	1.203	169	422	1.062	1.653	1.611.710.000	26,21
2	2012	1.051	132	261	810	1.203	1.639.240.000	19,07
3	2013	961	133	257	912	1.302	2.212.215.000	20,64
4	2014	781	115	228	716	1.059	2.061.865.000	16,79
5	2015	810	117	56	917	1.090	1.887.930.000	17,28
N =		4.806	666	1.224	4.417	6.307	9.412.960.000	100

The Overview of Traffic Accident in Perintis Kemerdekaan Street Makassar

Components Involved Traffic Accidents

According to the function that the is Perintis Kemerdekaan Street classified in the class arterial road that connects directly between Makassar City Maros. The area around this road are filled with educational areas, offices, commercial and industrial areas.

Table 2 portrays the frequency of road accidents Perintis Kemerdekaan Street. From the table shows that the highest accident rate in the year 2011 with the percentage reached 24.4%, equivalent to 172 events on this road. While the lowest frequency occurred in 2014 as much as 15.6%, equivalent to 110 events. Thus the frequency averaged 141 cases of accidents on this road.

Table 2 Number of Traffic Accidents on Printis Kemerdekaan Street

No	Year	Frequency Of Accidents	Percentage (%)
1	2011	172	24,40
2	2012	132	18,72
3	2013	164	23,26
4	2014	110	15,60
5	2015	127	18,01
Jumlah		705	100

In Fig 3 shows seven (7) types of components, the highest traffic accident that occurred in the highest Perintis Kemerdekaan Street. The highest components caused by the interaction between a motorcycle with a motorcycle that reaches 195 events over the last 5 years. Followed by the next highest component due to the interaction between a motorcycle with the car reached 193 instances. While accidents between pedestrians and automobiles is the lowest component with a total of 21 cases.

Fig. 3 Components of the highest traffic accident traffic

The Fatality Rate

Fig 4 shows that the fatality rate of road traffic accidents Perintis Kemerdekaan Street from year to year gives a figure high enough. The high fatality rate occurred in the year 2011 the number of victims as many as 248 people by the number of accident cases 172 cases. And in 2012 was the lowest accident frequency, the number of victims of this year amounted to 143 people with the number of cases as many as 132 events.

Fig 4. The number of victims of accidents by fatality

Typical of Vehicle Involved Accident

Judging from the type of vehicle involved in the accident can be seen in Table 3. Type of Vehicle involved in an accident highest in the last five years due to the motorcycle as much as 837 vehicles or equivalent 65.39% of the overall vehicle for 5 (five) years. Followed the car as much as 28.52% or as much as 365 vehicles of this type involved in the accident. While the smallest is 10-wheel trucks just as much as one vehicle involved in the Independence Pioneer Road segment during the last five years.

Table 3. The number of vehicles involved in traffic accidents

Type Of Vehicle	Year					Jumlah	Percentage (%)
	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015		
Motorcycles	205	146	194	129	163	837	65,39
Light Vehicle	77	70	92	66	60	365	28,52
Truck (6 wheels)	16	19	12	7	13	67	5,23
Becak	1					1	0,08
Bus	1	1				2	0,16
Bicycle		1		1	1	3	0,23
Bentor		1	1	2		4	0,31
Truck (10 wheels)				1		1	0,08
Numbers	300	238	299	206	237	1.280	100

The high number of accidents involving motorcyclists cannot be separated from the behavior of motorcyclists. Driver's unsafe behavior, such as speeding, trailing another vehicle too closely and running red lights and inconsiderate inconsiderate is an event commonly seen. These behaviors are behaviors of aggressive driving, which driving behavior is intentional, tend to increase the risk of collision and is motivated by impatience, annoyance, hostility or an attempt to save time. (Tasca, 2000).

The high number of accidents caused partly by high levels of congestion. As a result, there is some congestion points such as the front Makassar Town Square (MTOS), intersection of Unhas gate I and Unhas gate II, intersection of Lanraki, Power Intersection, KIMA Region, Batara Bira intersection and Airport intersection. This congestion raises a very high degree of saturation in this segment. Perintis Kemerdekaan Street on the degree of saturation at some point reached a value of 0.998. For IHCM standard, the degree of saturation that is considered good is the value below 0.75. The degree of saturation above 0.75 indicates the performance of the road to be repaired. From the results of these

evaluations indicate the performance of the Perintis Kemerdekaan Street is already in a critical state and unstable (Muis, 2013).

Accidents Classified according to Time

In Table 4 can be seen when the incidence of traffic accidents. The table shows that the frequency of occurrence of the highest traffic accident occurred in the morning that is between the hours of 00:00 to 10:00 of 38.87%, equivalent to 274 events over the last five years. The incidence and frequency of the next happens at night that the incident which took place in the period from hours 19:00 to 00:00, the events of this period, there were 178 incidents or by 25.25%.

Table 4. Time of occurrence of traffic accidents

Time	Year					Numbers	Percentage (%)
	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015		
00:00 - 10:00	65	44	74	42	49	274	38,87
10:00 - 15:00	35	26	27	26	27	141	20,00
15:00 - 19:00	22	25	25	20	20	112	15,89
19:00 - 00:00	50	37	38	22	31	178	25,25
Numbers	172	132	164	110	127	705	100,00

The high number of accidents in the morning on the Perintis Kemerdekaan Street provides an indication that the high number of trips will give you a direct impact on accidents. As we know that the area around the Perintis Kemerdekaan Street dominated by residential areas, education, office and industrial. Thereby giving effect to the tug and the seizure of the Perintis Kemerdekaan Neighborhood Street.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results if the statistics from this study can be drawn to some conclusions as follows that the number of traffic accidents in the city of Makassar in the period of last five years, reaching 3,603 cases with the highest number of cases reached 1,203 cases in 2011 and the lowest was 781 cases in 2014. material losses every year to reach RP. 1.8 billion million and the average number of victims as much as 1,261 people / year. The frequency of occurrence of traffic accidents over the past five years as many as 705 cases with the highest frequency of accidents in the year 2011 as many as 172 cases, or approximately 24.4%. The number of victims of traffic accidents was 959 inhabitants by category died, 84 people, 185 people were seriously injured and slightly injured 690 people. The highest cause of traffic accidents caused by motorcycles namely 65.39%, especially among motorcycle collisions of 195 events. The frequency higher incidence of traffic accidents occurred in the morning peak hours is 38.87%.

REFERENCES

Adisasmita, S. A. (2010). Planning and Road Network. Makassar: Faculty of Shipping UNHAS. (in Indonesian)

Aulia Sakti Internasional, PT. (2006). Preparation of General Plan Land Transport Safety. Jakarta: Ministry of Transport, Directorate General of Land Transportation. (in Indonesian)

Government Regulations. (1993). No. 43, *About Infrastructure and Road Traffic*. Indonesia. (in Indonesian)

Hoobs, F. (1995). Planning and Traffic Engineering. Edisi II. Jogjakarta: Gajah Mada University Press. (in Indonesian)

Karacasu, M., Analysis of Er, A., Bilgiç, S., & Barut, H. B. (2011). An Analysis on Distribution of Traffic Faults in Accidents, Based on Driver’s Age and Gender: Eskisehir Case. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 776–785.

Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 22 Year 2009 regarding Traffic and Road Transportation. Jakarta: Visimedia. (in Indonesian)

Muis, M. (2013). Characteristics Model Traffic On Perintis Kemerdekaan Street In Makassar. Retrieved May 31, 2016, from <http://repository.unhas.ac.id/handle/123456789/7154>. (in Indonesian)

Priiliawito, E., & Budiawati, A. (2014, Januari 26). Terrible death rate On the road Exceed Victim War Bay. Retrieved April 17, 2016, from <http://www.viva.co.id/http://fokus.news.viva.co.id/news/read/476357-mengerikan--angka-kematian-di-jalan-lampau-korban-perang-teluk>.(in Indonesian)

Tahir, A. (2006). Study Causes Traffic Accidents In Surabaya. *MEKTEK*, 91-99. (in Indonesian)

Tasca, L. (2000). *A Review Of the literature On Aggressive Driving Research*. Retrieved Desember 25, 2016, from <http://www.stopandgo.org/research/aggressive/tasca.pdf>.

Traffic Accident Unit, (2016). City Traffic Accident Data Makassar. Makassar: Polrestabes Kota Makassar. (in Indonesian)

Warpani, S. P. (2002). Traffic Management and Road Transport. Bandung: Bandung Institute of Technology. (in Indonesian)